

Dynamical Regimes and Phase Structure in Relativistic Rotation

Alexander Rozenkevich

Annotation

It is shown that relativistic rotation generates a metric ejection along the rotation axis. Rotation possesses an intrinsically observable geometric structure and defines a preferred axis. The number of revolutions contain invariant information about the motion that is independent of the observer. Since the phase quantity is related to the action of the system, it inherits its invariance. Accordingly, the ratio of two phases of a single relativistic rotational system acquires invariance in a broad sense, as it represents a ratio of two scalars.

A normalized phase parameter η is introduced, defined as the ratio of the current phase to the limiting phase. This parameter reflects the existence of a limiting velocity and allows the explicit time variable to be eliminated, leading to a geometric description of the system dynamics. Phase transitions corresponding to the equality of the tangential velocity and the ejection velocity are analyzed. Particular attention is given to regimes in which the ejection velocity reaches the speed of light even at relatively low tangential velocities.

The resulting phase diagram reveals one stable rotational region ($\eta \approx 0.24 - 0.3$) and two regions associated with conditions for metric ejection ($\eta \rightarrow 1$ and $\eta \rightarrow 0$). Metric ejection denotes the emergence of an additional orthogonal dynamical component associated with the restructuring of the effective geometry generated by relativistic rotation

Keywords: Special relativity, relativistic rotation, phase portrait

1. Introduction

Unlike translational motion, rotation possesses an intrinsically observable geometric structure and defines a preferred axis. The

number of completed revolutions is an absolute quantity and cannot be eliminated by a change of reference frame.

It is precisely the accumulation of angular phase that makes the phase description a natural language for rotational dynamics. In the proposed model, the state of the system is determined not by time, but by the degree of phase accumulation, characterized by the normalized parameter

$$\eta = \varphi_x / \varphi_c$$

where φ_x corresponds to the current rotational phase, and φ_c defines the limiting phase associated with the relativistic constraint of the system. This approach allows the relativistic limit to be treated as a constraint on the admissible phase structure of rotation, and enables a transition from a time-based description to the geometry of phase transitions between distinct dynamical regimes.

2. Basic formulas

In the works [3,4] it is shown that the movement of the metric along the axis of rotation z of a massless sphere is equal to:

$$z(\omega, r, \theta) = r \cos \theta - \frac{\sqrt{3}c}{2\omega} \ln \left(1 - \frac{r^2 \sin^2(\theta) \omega^2}{c^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

Therefore, with constant angular acceleration, the motion of α_z the metric in the vertical direction occurs with a velocity

$$v_z = \frac{dz}{dt} = \alpha_z \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}c}{2\omega^2} \ln \left(1 - \frac{r^2 \sin^2(\theta) \omega^2}{c^2} \right) + \frac{\sqrt{3} r^2 c \sin^2(\theta)}{c^2 - r^2 \sin^2(\theta) \omega^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

At the equator ($\theta = \pi/2$) the horizontal (tangential) velocity is maximum:

$$\frac{v_z}{c} = \frac{\sqrt{3} \alpha_z}{\omega_z^2} \left[\frac{1}{2} \ln \left(1 - \left(\frac{\omega_z}{\omega_c} \right)^2 \right) + \frac{\left(\frac{\omega_z}{\omega_c} \right)^2}{1 - \left(\frac{\omega_z}{\omega_c} \right)^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

Where: $\omega_z = \omega_{0z} + \alpha_z * t$, angular velocity.

here ω_{0z} - initial angular velocity,

α_z - angular acceleration;

t - time;

c - the speed of light.

$\omega_c = \frac{c}{r}$ - The limiting angular velocity for a given

radius of the sphere.

3. Initial transformations

The ratio of centripetal (normal) acceleration (a_n) to tangential acceleration (a_τ) is:

$$\tan \theta_x = \frac{a_n}{a_\tau} = \frac{\omega_z^2 r}{\alpha_z r} = \frac{\omega_z^2}{\alpha_z} = \alpha_z t^2 \quad (4)$$

θ_x — the angle of deviation of the total acceleration vector from the tangential velocity vector.

In equation (4), only the angular acceleration is constant:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_z &= \text{const} \\ a_n &\sim t^2 \end{aligned}$$

Equations (4) show that the ratio of accelerations depends linearly on the path (phase) traveled. The larger the phase, the closer the resulting acceleration towards the center of rotation.

To exclude the time variable and move on to a purely geometric description, we express the velocity as a function of phase φ_x .

With uniformly accelerated motion from rest:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_x &= \frac{\alpha_z t^2}{2} \rightarrow t^2 = \frac{\omega_z^2}{\alpha_z^2} \\ \varphi_x &= \frac{\omega_z^2}{2 \alpha_z} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where: φ_x - angular rotation around the Z axis, phase,
Compare with (4), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \tan \theta_x &= \frac{a_n}{a_\tau} = 2\varphi_x \\ \varphi_x &= \frac{1}{2} \tan \theta_x \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Find the angular velocity and tangential velocity from the phase:

$$\omega_z^2 = 2\varphi_x \alpha_z ,$$

$$\beta_x = \frac{r\omega_z}{c}$$

$$\beta_x = \frac{\omega_z}{\omega_c} = \frac{\sqrt{2\varphi_x\alpha_z}}{\omega_c} ,$$

$$\beta_x^2 = \frac{2\varphi_x\alpha_z}{\omega_c^2} = \frac{2\varphi_x}{2\varphi_c} = \frac{\varphi_x}{\varphi_c} \rightarrow \beta_x = \left(\frac{\varphi_x}{\varphi_c}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Where: β_x - tangential (horizontal velocity) in units of the speed of light;

φ_c - Maximum allowable phase value for this system:

$$\varphi_c = \frac{\omega_c^2}{2\alpha_z}$$

Next, enter the designations:

$$\eta = \frac{\varphi_x}{\varphi_c} ,$$

$$\beta_x = \frac{\omega_z}{\omega_c} = \frac{v_x}{c} = \eta^{\frac{1}{2}} ,$$

$$\beta_z = \frac{v_z}{c} = \frac{v_z}{v_x} \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Here:

η - normalized phase, the ratio of the current phase to the limiting phase.

β_z - is the speed parallel to the axis of rotation (the speed of the ejection of the metric), in units of the speed of light.

Finding a connection with accelerations:

$$\frac{d\beta_x}{dt} = a_\tau , \quad \frac{d\beta_n}{dt} = a_n$$

Where β_n - normal velocity to the center of curvature.

Substituting:

$$a_\tau = \alpha_x r , \quad a_n = \omega_z^2 r , \quad \omega_z = \alpha_x t$$

We integrate:

Tangent Velocity

$$\beta_x = \int a_t dt = \alpha_z rt$$

Normal velocity, to the center of curvature:

$$\beta_n = \int a_n dt = \alpha_z^2 r t^2 dt = \frac{1}{3} \alpha_z^2 r t^3$$

Making a substitution:

$$\beta_n = \frac{\alpha_z^2 r t^3}{3} = \frac{4\alpha_z^2 r t^3}{4 \cdot 3} = \frac{4\varphi_x^2 r}{3t} = \frac{4}{3} \varphi_x^2 \beta_r$$

Here:

$$\beta_r = \frac{r}{t}$$

- Scale estimation of radius change rate

Definitions of the velocities

- β_n — normal velocity associated with the curvature of the trajectory. In the present model, it is interpreted as a consequence of spatial expansion rather than its primary cause.
- β_r — radial deformation velocity associated with variations in the system scale. The quantity

$$\beta_r = \frac{r}{t}$$

acts as a scalar measure of spatial expansion. At each point, it characterizes the rate of change of the radial coordinate along the world line.

In cosmological analogy,

$$\frac{\beta_r}{r}$$

corresponds to the Hubble parameter. If $\beta_r \neq 0$, space undergoes expansion or contraction. If $\beta_r = 0$, the geometry remains static, and

only spatial curvature is present (for example, a static spherical geometry without evolution).

This relation suggests that the Hubble expansion may arise as a consequence of rotational geometry rather than as an independent property of the Universe.

Other velocities

- β_τ (tangential velocity) — associated with rotation in an expanding geometry.
- β_z (axial ejection velocity) — interpreted as the projection of expansion onto the preferred rotation axis.

Velocity ratio

$$\frac{\beta_n}{\beta_x} = \frac{\alpha_z t^2}{3} = \frac{\omega_z t}{3} = \frac{2}{3} \varphi_x, \quad \lambda = \frac{v_z}{v_x} = \frac{\beta_z}{\beta_x} \quad (7)$$

4. Phase portrait of a rotating model

Substituting the entered notations in (3), we get:

$$\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x} \left[\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - \beta_x^2) + \frac{\beta_x^2}{1 - \beta_x^2} \right] \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) shows the dependence of the orthogonal (along the axis) velocity on the horizontal (tangential) velocity.

Functionality:

$$F(\beta_x) = \left[\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - \beta_x^2) + \frac{\beta_x^2}{1 - \beta_x^2} \right] \quad (9)$$

or

$$F(\eta) = \left[\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - \eta) + \frac{\eta}{1 - \eta} \right] \quad (10)$$

It contains two singularities: logarithmic and rational. The first term is associated with the Lorentz factor (γ_x), the second term is dynamic. Therefore, we can write:

$$\text{contain} \quad F(\beta_x) = -\ln(\gamma_x) + \gamma_x^2 \beta_x^2, \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Where:} \quad \gamma_x = \sqrt{\frac{1}{1-\beta_x^2}}, \text{ Lorentz factor}$$

Rewrite equation (9)

$$\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x} F(\beta_x) \quad (12)$$

Or:

$$\beta_z = \frac{v_z}{v_x} \eta^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x} F(\eta) \quad (13)$$

$$\left(\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_c \eta} F(\eta) \right)$$

$$\beta_x = \eta^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x \lambda} F(\eta) \quad (14)$$

$$\left(\beta_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\eta \varphi_c \lambda} F(\eta) \right)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}} F(\eta) \quad (15)$$

$$\left(\lambda = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_c \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}} F(\eta) \right)$$

$$\varphi_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\beta_z} F(\eta) \quad (16)$$

$$\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3} \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}}{3\beta_n} F(\eta)$$

5. Examples

Let's consider five scenarios:

1. Centripetal (normal) acceleration is equal to tangential acceleration:

$$\frac{a_n}{a_\tau} = 2\varphi_x = 1$$

Therefore:

$$\varphi_x = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\eta = \frac{\varphi_x}{\varphi_c} = \frac{1}{2\varphi_c}$$

Substituting (13) into formula

$$\frac{\sqrt{3}}{\beta_z} F(\eta) = 1$$

$$\beta_z = \sqrt{3} F(\eta)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}} F(\eta)$$

2. The normal velocity towards the center of rotation is equal to the tangential velocity.

In accordance with (7):

$$\frac{\beta_n}{\beta_x} = \frac{2}{3} \varphi_x = 1$$

$$\varphi_x = \frac{3}{2}$$

Substituting in (14) , we get:

$$\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}F(\eta)}{3}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} \frac{F(\eta)}{\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

3. The normal velocity is equal to the scale estimate of the rate of change of the radius:

$$\beta_n = \beta_r$$

$$\beta_n = \frac{4}{3} \varphi_x^2 \beta_r$$

$$\varphi_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

In accordance with (16)

$$\varphi_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\beta_z} F(\eta)$$

$$\beta_z = F(\eta)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{F(\eta)}{\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

4. The velocity along the axis (ejection velocity) is equal to the horizontal (tangential) velocity.

$$\lambda = \frac{\beta_z}{\beta_x} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}} F(\eta)$$

Therefore:

$$\varphi_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\lambda\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}} F(\eta)$$

$$\varphi_c = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\lambda\eta^{\frac{3}{2}}} F(\eta)$$

$$\lambda\varphi_c = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\eta^2} F(\eta)$$

$$\varphi_c = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\eta^2} F(\eta)$$

$$\beta_z = \beta_x = \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

5. The speed in the normal direction is equal to the speed along the axis of rotation.

$$\beta_z = \beta_n$$

From (7)

$$\lambda = \frac{\beta_n}{\beta_x} = \frac{\beta_z}{\beta_x} = \frac{2}{3}\varphi_x \quad , \quad \beta_n = \frac{2}{3}\varphi_x\beta_x = \frac{2}{3}\varphi_x\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Using (13), the result is:

$$\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}}{3\beta_n} F(\eta) \quad \beta_z^2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}}{3} F(\eta)$$

$$\beta_z = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}}{3} F(\eta)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} F(\eta)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

To build a phase portrait:

From (15)

$$\lambda = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}} F(\eta) = \frac{2}{3}\varphi_x$$

After small transformations, we get:

$$\varphi_c = \frac{16}{27} \frac{\varphi_x^5}{F^2(\eta)} \quad , \quad \varphi_x = \eta\varphi_c$$

$$\varphi_c = \left(\frac{27F^2(\eta)}{16\eta^5}\right)^{1/4}$$

$$\varphi_c = 1.1398 \frac{F^{\frac{1}{2}}(\eta)}{\eta^{\frac{5}{4}}}$$

$$\varphi_x = 1.1398 \frac{F^{\frac{1}{2}}(\eta)}{\eta^{\frac{1}{4}}}$$

Determine the scale estimate of the rate of change of the radius:

$$\beta_n = \frac{4}{3} \varphi_x^2 \beta_r = \beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x} F(\eta)$$

$$\beta_r = \frac{r}{t} = \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8} \cdot \frac{F(\eta)}{\varphi_x^3}$$

We substitute (16), we get:

$$\beta_z = (\beta_r F(\eta)^2)^{1/3}$$

The speed in the direction of the axis of rotation is equal to the speed of light.

$$\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x} F(\eta) = 1$$

Therefore:

$$\varphi_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} F(\eta)$$

$$\varphi_c = \frac{\sqrt{3} F(\eta)}{2\eta}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\beta_z}{\beta_x} = \frac{1}{\beta_x} = \frac{1}{\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

Table 1 Fundamental variables and dynamical parameters
 Table 2 shows the phase portraits of the model with characteristic parameters.

Tabl.1

φ_x	- Angular rotation around an axis Z, phase	$\varphi_x = \frac{\omega_z^2}{2 \alpha_z}$
φ_c	- maximum allowable phase value for a given system	$\varphi_c = \frac{\omega_c^2}{2 \alpha_z}$
$F(\eta)$	Features	$F(\eta) = \left[\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - \eta) + \frac{\eta}{1 - \eta} \right]$
η	normalized phase parameter	$\eta = \frac{\varphi_x}{\varphi_c}$
β_x	Tangential horizontal speed	$\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$
β_z	Vertical Velocity Parallel to Axis of Rotation (Axial Ejection)	$\beta_z = \frac{v_z}{v_x} \eta^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_x} \cdot F(\eta)$ $\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\varphi_c} \cdot \frac{F(\eta)}{\eta}$
λ	<i>Ratio of ejection velocity to tangential velocity</i>	$\lambda = \frac{\beta_z}{\beta_x}$
β_n	<i>Normal Velocity to Center of Curvature</i>	$\beta_n = \frac{1}{3} \alpha_z^2 r t^3$

β_r	Scaling Estimate of the Rate of Change of Radius	$\beta_r = \frac{r}{t}$
-----------	--	-------------------------

Tabl.2

	Parametric Requirements	Completion Conditions				
		General		Key points		
				Ejection velocity is equal to horizontal velocity	The speed of ejection is equal to the speed of light $\beta_z = 1$	Other properties
1	$\frac{a_n}{a_\tau} = 1$	$\varphi_x = \frac{1}{2}$	$\beta_z = \sqrt{3}F(\eta)$ $\lambda_1 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{\frac{1}{\eta^2}}F(\eta)$	$\eta = 0.366$ $\lambda_1 = 1$	$\eta = 0.4725$ $\lambda_1 = 1.455$	
2	$\frac{\beta_n}{\beta_x} = 1$	$\varphi_x = \frac{3}{2}$	$\beta_z = \frac{\sqrt{3}F(\eta)}{2}$ $\lambda_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \frac{F(\eta)}{\frac{1}{\eta^2}}$	$\eta \approx 0.67$ $\lambda_1 = 1$	$\eta \approx 0.7$ $\lambda_1 = 1.2$	$\eta = 0.6$ $\lambda_2 = 0.78$ $\beta_x = \beta_n = \beta_z$
3	$\frac{\beta_r}{\beta_n} = 1$	$\varphi_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$	$\beta_z = F(\eta)$ $\lambda_3 = \frac{F(\eta)}{\frac{1}{\eta^2}}$	$\eta \approx 0.53$ $\lambda_1 = 1$	$\eta \approx 0.6$ $\lambda_1 = 1.29$	
4	$\lambda = \frac{\beta_z}{\beta_x} = 1$	$\varphi_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\eta^2} \cdot F(\eta)$	$\beta_z = \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ $\lambda_4 = 1$	There is a minimum φ_c with $\eta = \eta^* \approx 0.26$, $\varphi_x \approx 0.341$, $\varphi_c \approx 1.312$		Phase change line. Emission boundary.

5	$\frac{\beta_z}{\beta_n} = 1$	$\varphi_x = 1.1398 F$	$\beta_z = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3} \eta^2}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot F(\eta)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ $\beta_r = \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8} \cdot \frac{F(\eta)}{\varphi_x^3}$ $\beta_z = (\beta_r F(\eta)^2)^{1/3}$ $\lambda_5 = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} F(\eta)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$\eta \approx 0.7 \lambda_1 = 1$	$\eta \approx 0.75 \lambda_1 = 1.15$	Radius Change Rate: $\beta_r = \frac{r}{t} = \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8} \cdot \frac{F(\eta)}{\varphi_x^3}$ $\beta_z = (\beta_r F(\eta)^2)^{1/3}$ $\eta = 0.6 \lambda_5 = 0.78$ $\beta_x = \beta_n = \beta_z$
6	$\beta_z = 1$	$\varphi_x = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} F(\eta)$	$\beta_z = 1$ $\lambda_6 = \frac{1}{\eta^2}$			Ejection along the axis at the speed of light

1. -Centripetal (normal) acceleration is equal to tangential acceleration
2. - The normal velocity towards the center of rotation is equal to the tangential velocity.
3. - The normal velocity is equal to the scale estimate of the rate of change of the radius
4. - The vertical velocity along the axis is equal to the horizontal (tangential) velocity.
5. - The velocity in the normal direction is equal to the velocity along the axis of rotation z
6. - The speed along the axis of rotation is equal to the speed of light.

6. Analysis of the results

6.1 Phase transition diagram (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1 shows a diagram of phase transitions of the dynamics of relativistic rotation. Each curve $\lambda_i(\eta)$ determines the boundary of equality of two dynamic parameters and divides the areas of dominance of the corresponding components of the motion Normalized phase parameter:

$$\eta = \frac{\varphi_x}{\varphi_c}$$

characterizes the degree of approximation of the system to the limiting relativistic state and reflects the existence of a finite speed of propagation of interactions. Using this parameter η allows you to move from a temporal description to a geometric analysis of dynamic modes.

The obtained dependencies show that different mechanisms of rotational dynamics achieve ejection conditions at different values η . Each curve λ_i crosses the border

$$\lambda = 1,$$

corresponding to the moment of occurrence of the axial ejection, in its characteristic range of phase parameters:

$$\lambda_1: \eta \approx 0.366,$$

$$\lambda_2: \eta \approx 0.66,$$

$$\lambda_3: \eta \approx 0.57,$$

$$\lambda_5: \eta \approx 0.70.$$

Thus, each physical mechanism has its own scenario for the transition from a stationary rotational mode to an axial ejection mode.

6.2 Sub light and light velocities along the axis of rotation

We can see that it is possible to achieve light velocity along the axis of rotation at relatively small values of horizontal tangential velocity. For example, if centripetal and tangential accelerations are equal, the ejection at the speed of light along the axis of rotation occurs already at a horizontal velocity of the order of $0.67c$ and at the values of

$$\eta < 0.5.$$

At the same time, the equality of horizontal and axial velocities is achieved much earlier — at

$$\eta \approx 0.366.$$

The results obtained indicate the existence of a region of accelerated growth of the axial component of motion, which arises even before the system reaches the limiting relativistic state.

The model considers the kinematic motion of a virtually massless structure, so the resulting velocities should not be interpreted as an ordinary vector addition of velocities in one space. The axial ejection is the appearance of a new orthogonal metric component of motion associated with the rearrangement of the geometry of the system. For this reason, the β_z can exceed one without violating the local constraints of special relativity. The horizontal and axial components are dynamically connected, but the corresponding metric structures remain orthogonal and describe independent geometric directions of the system's evolution.

6.3 Phase transition boundary (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2 shows the phase transition line in coordinates

$$\begin{aligned} & (\varphi_c, \eta), \\ \text{Compliant} & \\ & \lambda = 1. \end{aligned}$$

This curve separates the two areas of dynamic modes:

- Stationary rotation region ($\lambda < 1$);
- Axial Discharge Area ($\lambda > 1$).

Of particular interest is the presence of a single minimum function $\varphi_c(\eta)$, which corresponds to the most probable area of origin of the release, since it is at this critical point that the system needs minimal external influence to cross the stability boundary.

The critical point is determined by the parameters (Table 3) : $\eta^* \approx 0.26$, $\varphi_x^* \approx 0.341$, $\varphi_c^{min} \approx 1.312$

Tabl.3

η	φ_c
0.24	1.3153
0.25	1.312841
0.255	1.312108
0.256	1.311999
0.257	1.311904
0.25705	1.311899
0.2571	1.311895
0.2572	1.311886
0.2573	1.311877
0.26	1.311692
0.27	1.311776
0.28	1.31303
0.29	1.315402
0.3	1.318849
0.301	1.319251

6.4 Critical point and asymmetry

The resulting phase structure demonstrates the existence of three different dynamic modes:

- with $\eta \rightarrow 0$ the system remains unstable and does not form a stationary rotational structure;
- in the field of

$$\eta \approx 0.24 - 0.3$$

a stable mode of rotation appears;

- with

$$\eta \rightarrow 1$$

The system approaches the relativistic limit, which is accompanied by the development of an axial ejection.

Thus, the classic limit

$$\eta \rightarrow 0$$

does not correspond to the stable state of the system. In contrast to standard relativistic representations, the region of small values of η is characterized by the absence of a formed dynamic structure and increased sensitivity to the occurrence of axial ejection. Consequently, stability does not arise at vanishingly small values of the phase parameter, but only at finite values of η . This leads to the existence of two different modes of ejection appearance:

-initial outburst at low η associated with the lack of a formed structure;

-relativistic outburst at

$$\eta \rightarrow 1,$$

due to the achievement of the maximum geometric configuration of the system.

The resulting diagram shows the existence of one region of stability and two regions of origin of the outlier.

A practical consequence of the model is that long-lived relativistic emissions should form in the vicinity of the found minimum $(\eta^*, \varphi_c^{min})$, where the transition to the emission mode requires minimal changes to the system parameters.

The minimum plays the role of a threshold for the formation of the structure: on the left, the system switches to the mode of ejection, on the right, to the mode of stable existence.

There is no symmetry in the region of the minimum in terms of consequences:

$$\eta^* - \delta \neq \eta^* + \delta$$

That is:

- mathematically the displacements are small,
- physically - the consequences are radically different.

The structure either "does not have time to be born" or begins to live for a long time.

The asymmetries around the minimum affect the geometry of the phase space, the stability of the system occurs close to the maximum critical region.

6.5 Observation criteria

The observational criterion of the model can be the comparison of the rotation and ejection parameters of astrophysical objects with the found critical region. If the calculated values φ_x, φ_c will be located near the found minimum, this will be an argument in favor of the proposed model.

6.6 Indicator after bifurcation

After the bifurcation ($\lambda > 1$), a new kinematic branch appears, and the tempo of time along the X-axis becomes substantially greater than along the Z-axis:

$$\tau_x > \tau_z.$$

This corresponds to the emergence of inflationary growth of the vertical component of the velocity and can be interpreted as the birth of a new effective metric related to the phase dynamics of the system.

Fig.1

Fig.2

The phase diagram shows the boundary of the stationary regime ($\lambda = 1$) and the relativistic limit ($\beta z = 1$). The physically feasible ejection mode is limited to the region between these curves. Steady rotation exists near $\eta = 0.24-0.3$, while low and high values of η correspond to instability.

Conclusion

The phase structure of relativistic rotation has been investigated within a model linking rotational dynamics to the emergence of axial metric ejection. A normalized phase parameter is introduced,

$$\eta = \frac{\varphi_x}{\varphi_c} = \frac{\int \omega dt}{\varphi_c}$$

which characterizes the degree to which the system approaches its limiting relativistic state and enables a transition from a time-based description to a geometric analysis of dynamical regimes.

It is shown that different mechanisms of rotational dynamics reach ejection conditions at different values of η , forming a system of phase transitions between the stationary regime and the regime of axial ejection. The obtained dependencies demonstrate the existence of a distinguished boundary

$$\lambda = 1$$

corresponding to the equality of the tangential and axial velocity components.

It is established that a stable rotational regime exists only within a limited region of phase parameters,

$$\eta \approx 0.25 - 0.3$$

whereas both limiting regimes prove to be unstable:

- at $\eta \rightarrow 0$ the structure fails to form and the system may transition into an early axial ejection regime;
- at $\eta \rightarrow 1$ the system reaches the relativistic limit, accompanied by the development of ejection along the rotation axis.

Thus, stability arises not in the classical limit of small phases, but only at finite values of the governing parameter η .

Of particular interest is the existence of a unique minimum on the phase transition boundary. It is shown that this region possesses a sharply asymmetric dynamical structure: a small displacement toward lower values of η leads to a transition into the ejection regime, whereas a displacement in the opposite direction gives rise to a stable long-lived rotational state.

Thus, the identified minimum plays the role of a structure formation threshold and separates two fundamentally distinct dynamical regions — early ejection and stable existence of the system.

Within the framework of the model, axial ejection is interpreted not as ordinary motion of a material object in a single space, but as the

emergence of a new orthogonal metric component of dynamics. Therefore, values of

$$\beta_z > 1$$

do not contradict the local constraints of special relativity and reflect a geometric restructuring of the system.

The obtained results admit astrophysical interpretation. In particular, long-lived relativistic ejections may form in the vicinity of the identified critical region, where the system combines high stability with maximum sensitivity to the transition into the axial ejection regime.

The proposed model admits further development in the directions of analysis of the metric geometry of rotation, the phase structure of relativistic regimes, and possible observational manifestations of axial ejections in astrophysical systems.

It is possible that relativistic constraints may be interpreted because of restrictions on the admissible phase structure of rotation.

References

- 1 . Guth, A. H. (1981). "The Inflationary Universe: A Possible Solution to the Horizon and Flatness Problems". *Physical Review D*.
- 2 . Linde, A. (2014). "Inflationary Cosmology after Planck 2013". [arXiv:1402.0526](https://arxiv.org/abs/1402.0526).
- 3 . Alexander Rozenkevich, Deformation of a Rotating Dust Disk within the Framework of Special Relativity, <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.31353397>, 2026
- 4 .Alexander Rozenkevich , Relativistic rotating dust-like sphere of infinitesimal mass, <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.31386115>, 2026
- 5 .Alexander Rozenkevich , A Kinematic Functional in Cosmic Inflation Reveals a Dynamic Relation Between e and π (Error 0–0.15%), <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.31376059>
- 6 .A Snapshot of Relativistic Motion: Visualizing the Terrell Effect, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.04296>, 6 Sep 2024